

FEATURES OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT AND LEADERSHIP STYLES IN A GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL COMMUNITY

Saidqulov Sodiqjon Botirovich,

National Institute of Pedagogical Skills named after

Abdulla Avloni Doctoral student

saidqulovsodiqjon@gmail.com

Abstract: *This article analyzes the characteristics of the relationship between the management styles of school principals and the social environment in schools. Based on these analyses, recommendations are developed for the principal regarding methods for developing the social environment in his management activities.*

Key words: *director, teacher, social environment, style, attitude, communication, cooperation, mediation*

The main goal of the reforms currently being carried out in the general secondary education system is to improve the quality and efficiency of education in schools. The success of the educational process depends not only on the curricula, teaching methods or material and technical base established in the state educational standard or state educational requirements, but also on the social environment formed in the school pedagogical team and the management style of the school principal.

The social environment is determined by factors such as the psychological climate between team members (director and teachers, teachers and students, teachers and parents, director and members of the public), mutual respect, cooperation, trust, support, and effective communication. In the formation of such a positive environment, the school principal's management style plays a decisive role. The leader's attitude towards employees, the participation of team members in the decision-making process, the culture of communication, management principles, and the prevention of possible conflicts can contribute to the emergence of a healthy or unhealthy psychological climate in the pedagogical team.

In the context of reforms in the modern education system, the effectiveness of school management largely depends on the leadership style and the social environment of the community. The large-scale reforms being implemented in the education system of Uzbekistan require the introduction of new approaches

based on the principles of democratic governance. Therefore, the school environment is considered a complex open system, in which the socio-psychological relationship between the leader and the teacher directly affects internal stability and the quality of education.

Leadership style is understood as a specific approach of a leader to solving a particular issue in the management process. When making decisions, organizing their implementation, and controlling the work of subordinates, a leader acts in accordance with his duties. However, each leader acts in his own way, using methods that are suitable for him in the management process, which determine his leadership style. Just as there are no two people who are absolutely identical, there is no absolutely identical style in leadership. In this regard, when describing leadership styles, it has become customary in the literature on social psychology and management to divide management methods into traditional and modern categories. In this regard, the scientific research of G. Gibsh, M. Forverg, B. Bass, D. Barrett, K. Baird, K. Levin, R. Likert, L. Berkovets, V. Heithorn, F. Fidler, D. McGregor and other scientists is worthy of praise.

The social environment of a school is an important factor in shaping leadership styles. The internal and external characteristics of the social environment determine which leadership style will be most effective. In particular, corporate culture is an important component of the internal life of the school, determining the nature of the relationship between teachers, students and administration. In addition, the educational process is influenced not only by internal factors, but also by external socio-political conditions.

The social context and environmental stability also affect the choice of leadership style. For example, if formal leaders dominate in stable conditions, the role of natural leaders increases during periods of reform or crisis.

In the scientific literature, various styles of leadership are distinguished - authoritarian, democratic, liberal and participative styles, each of which has a different impact on the social environment of the pedagogical community.

The authoritarian style is based on individual decision-making and strict control, which can provide discipline in the short term, but increases psychological pressure in the team. This style can provide discipline, but reduces initiative and creates tension in the team.

The democratic style is based on reliance on team opinion, distribution of responsibilities and trust. This style is based on mutual respect, open

communication and cooperation, and serves to create a healthy and social environment, and is considered the most optimal for creating a positive social environment.

The liberal style is characterized by minimal intervention by the leader and often leads to a weakening of control. This style is characterized by giving freedom to employees, but lack of control can lead to chaos in the team. As a modern approach, participatory management involves involving teachers in the decision-making process.

In the participatory style, it is determined that the leader will establish horizontal relations with subordinates in managing the pedagogical team.

As a result of the correct application of the school principal's management style, a positive social environment is formed in the school pedagogical team, the professional activity of teachers increases, the creative abilities of teachers are further developed, cooperation and mutual pedagogical assistance in the team are strengthened, and conflicts between the leader and teachers are prevented.

On the contrary, an unfavorable social environment can lead to stress, apathy, decreased initiative and professional fatigue in teachers. Therefore, the school principal's management style directly affects the general morale of the team, work efficiency and the quality of education.

The formation of a positive or negative social environment in secondary schools depends on management styles, on the one hand, and on the other hand, on the quality of the relationship between the head and teachers. In modern educational management approaches, the relationship between the head and the teacher is considered not only a central factor in the management process, but also the main mechanism determining the social environment in the school.

The effectiveness of the cooperation between the school principal and teachers transforms the social environment into a more stable, open and reliable system. Through this relationship, teachers feel valued, supported and development-oriented. This, in turn, has a positive effect on the academic success of students and the general social mood of the school community.

The above aspects were also emphasized in the opinions expressed at the II All-Russian Pedagogical Assembly, noting that the social role of the teacher, professional responsibility and cooperation with social institutions are decisive factors in the sustainable development of modern education.

Teaching activities are not limited to imparting knowledge, but are closely related to the transmission of cultural values, the formation of humanity and

strengthening social responsibility. In this regard, the relationship between the leader and the teacher is not only an element of the management process, but also the main mechanism that determines the social environment of an educational institution. The leader's communication with teachers based on mutual respect, trust and cooperation forms a healthy social climate in the school community, increases the professional activity of teachers and, in turn, ensures positive results in working with students.

In modern conditions of pedagogical activity, the teacher performs many social roles - he acts not only as a giver of knowledge, but also as a communicator, mediator, educator, social partner and propagator of culture. Therefore, the role of the leader in supporting these processes becomes even more important. Only when the school principal can see the teacher not only as a supervisor, but also as a partner, will the teacher fully demonstrate his professional potential. This, in turn, strengthens openness, solidarity and mutual trust in the social environment.

Effective communication between the teacher and the leader allows the school to transform from a closed system into an open system of social cooperation. In this approach, the educational institution is formed not only as a center of the educational process, but also as a social institution that actively interacts with society and promotes culture. In particular, collective discussions organized at the initiative of the leader, regular contacts with the parent committee ensure social cohesion in the school.

The role of the leader-pedagogue relationship in the formation of the social environment in general secondary schools is of particular importance. Studies conducted on the study of leader-pedagogue relationships show that mutual trust, support, and sincere communication between the school principal and the teacher are among the most important factors ensuring the stability of the social environment. By conducting open communication with the team, the school leader creates the opportunity for teachers to freely express their opinions, show initiative, and feel professional responsibility.

The culture of leadership based on humanism stimulates the social activity of teachers, encourages them to cooperate and exchange experiences. In this regard, the quality of the relationship between the leader and the teacher is one of the main indicators determining the level of the general social environment in the school. The results of the research of D. Edgerson, W. Kritsonis, D. Herrington show that in teams where mutual trust and justice prevail, there is high

motivation, professional loyalty, and mutual support of teachers in pedagogical processes. In such schools, the leader does not limit his activities to administrative control, but becomes a social partner of the pedagogical team. He creates conditions for the professional development of teachers, allows them to take the initiative, and supports innovations in the educational process. Thanks to this, the social climate in the school changes positively, teachers are satisfied with their work, a culture of communication develops, and students directly feel the positive impact of this environment.

Based on the research of Edgerson and co-authors, it can be said that the positive relationship between the leader and the teacher strengthens not only the internal social environment, but also the external reputation of the school. Because when the leader has a fair and open relationship with his team, this is reflected in the culture of the entire educational organization. Such a leadership model creates a “trusting cooperation environment” in the school, which is a guarantee of the stability and continuous development of the social environment. As a result, the relationship between the leader and the teacher is considered not only a management mechanism, but also a central element of a culture based on cooperation and trust, ensuring social stability. The school leader not only manages teachers administratively, but also enriches the social environment as a person who respects their professional values, sees them as partners. In this way, healthy communication and cultural cooperation between the leader and the teacher form an atmosphere of creativity, responsibility and social solidarity in the school.

As a conclusion of the theoretical, practical and research work mentioned above, we have developed several recommendations for the formation of positive leader-teacher relationships in schools:

Creating an open communication system. It is necessary to organize regular information exchange, open conversations, and meetings between the leader and the teacher. An “open door policy” - the leader’s readiness to listen to teachers’ suggestions or problems at any time - strengthens mutual trust in the school culture.

Sincere attention to the professional growth of teachers. The leader should not only be a person who makes demands on teachers, but also creates opportunities for their development. Creating opportunities for professional training, seminars, and learning best practices are powerful factors that positively affect the social environment.

Active participation of the leader in school life. The leader's attendance at classroom lessons, participation in educational events, and active participation in informal dialogues with the pedagogical team help to feel the leader's presence in the pedagogical team and strengthen team spirit.

Supporting the mental health and well-being of teachers. In modern management, leaders should take into account the psychological state of teachers. Programs aimed at stress management, recreation, and maintaining work-life balance - ensure a healthy social environment.

Creating a culture of inclusion and solidarity in the school community. The leader should establish positive communication not only with teachers, but also with students, parents, and support staff. This strengthens the school as a single social system.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Е. Ю. Немчинова. Социальная сущность лидеров и элит, процесс их взаимодействия и роль в развитии общества. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата философских наук, Москва-2011
2. E.O. Hayitov. Management Psychology-Textbook. Chirchik 2020.
3. U. Nurmatov. Socio-psychological characteristics of participatory management of the pedagogical team. Scientific, remote, online conference "Pedagogy and Psychology in the Modern World". 2024

